

OCTRI Usage and Impact

Unique Support and Resources for OHSU Research

ABOUT OCTRI

OCTRI has been NIH-funded since 2006 with current FY25 funding of \$11.7M (direct costs \$8.3M). OCTRI provides broad-based infrastructure to support and improve clinical and translational research at OHSU, enhance the clinical research workforce, and advance science that promotes efficient and effective research. OCTRI is a central resource with the following services open to all researchers at OHSU:

- Comprehensive clinical research support, including study start up; recruitment; Biostatistics, Epidemiology, and Research design (BERD); regulatory support; and the Clinical and Translational Research Center (CTRC)
- Informatics support for data management, custom applications, and leveraging EHR data
- Training in clinical and translational research skills and competencies for faculty and staff
- Funding and career development opportunities from two embedded training grants
- Support for community engaged research statewide through a regional liaison program and partnership with Oregon Rural Practice-based Research Network (ORPRN)
- Pilot funding for innovative biomedical and healthcare solutions, support for preliminary data generation, and stimulating the development of translational research

DATA RESOURCES

OCTRI provides a suite of data resources.

- REDCap is a web-based tool to support clinical research data collection. OCTRI supports training and administration of the tool, encompassing 1000+ active research protocols with ~4000 users.
- The Data Coordinating Center (DCC) is a comprehensive resource for trial design, management, innovation. In 2024, the DCC leveraged \$8.3M of clinical trial funding for investigator-initiated, multicenter trials.
- The OCTRI Informatics Innovation Core has provided expertise, including creating and maintaining custom applications, for sponsored research projects with over \$40M in funding since 2020.

Key takeaways about OCTRI

- Supported 57% of OHSU NIH-funded investigators and had an impact on 67% of NIH funding (Figure 1)
- Provides clinical research support via 10+ programs that supported 1800 projects in 2024 (Table 1)
- Provides unique services and resources to OHSU's research mission (e.g. REDCap, CTRC, BERD, RDW)
- Supports researchers in all schools, departments, and centers and is disease agnostic

FIGURE 1. OCTRI IMPACT FY 2024

INTEGRATED SHARED INFRASTRUCTURE

OCTRI's BERD team is seamlessly integrated with the USR Biostatistics and Design Program, supporting researchers from training and mentorship to study design and data analysis. In FY24, the BERD-BDP team provided 156 project consults, 181 advice sessions, and intensive mentorship for 20 early career awards.

The **Community, Outreach, Research, and Engagement (CORE) program** integrates community engagement teams at OCTRI, Knight Cancer Institute (KCI), and ORPRN, which maximizes the funding and infrastructure of each program while growing capacity for grant funded community research across Oregon.

OCTRI Informatics aligns strategically with the KCI to meet OHSU needs and efficiently leverage resources. OCTRI supplies automated data marts with integrated EHR and clinical genomics data for 9 KCI initiatives.

EDUCATION, TRAINING AND STAFF SUPPORT

OCTRI offers training opportunities for faculty, fellows, students, and study coordinators.

- Clinical research workforce members have accessed or attended in-person, online, and live on-demand and e-learning trainings almost 3000 times since 2023.

- The Human Investigations Program provides training for faculty, fellows, PhD students, and clinical fellows.
 - >1400 individuals trained since 2001
 - 553 Master of Clinical Research degrees and certificates awarded
 - 129 currently enrolled students

- Two embedded training grants that annually support 7 faculty members and 11 pre- and post-doc trainees. We actively support 3 other T32s and 4 K12 awards.
 - 89% of 2017-23 K program trainees have independent research funding
 - 87% of 2007-16 K program trainees have R01 or equivalent

- CTRC has provided a phlebotomy course to over 220 individuals from 20 departments since June 2020.

STUDY SUPPORT

OCTRI provides comprehensive study support services.

- Research navigators, a centralized entry point to access coordinated research support at OCTRI and across OHSU
- Free regulatory consults (100+ in 2024) that include data safety monitoring, FDA regulatory processes for IND/IDE, and broad human subjects guidance.

- CTRC provides an inpatient and outpatient facility with nurses, study coordinators, bionutritionists, and a sleep facility. In 2024, the bionutrition unit supported 9 depts with 200+ consults and 1100+ research meals; the sleep facility supported 5 RO1s from 4 investigators.
 - \$3.5M supported by bionutrition unit
 - \$2.5M supported by sleep facility

- Since StudyPages launched in April 2023, 1000+ individuals have signed up for 120 studies. OCTRI Recruitment trained 160+ personnel across 22 depts.
- OCTRI Recruitment provided 37 consults and assistance for grants and funded projects in 2024.

Table 1. OCTRI Programs supported over 1800 research projects in 2024

Program	Projects
REDCap	1225
CTRC	309
Informatics	89
Regulatory consults	115
Community	68
Evaluation Assistance Program	64
BERD/BDP grant submissions	67*
Recruitment assistance	37

Many projects use multiple OCTRI programs at the same time and across the lifespan of a project.

*CY 2023 data, all other CY 2024

PILOTS AWARDS, COMMUNITY ENGAGEMENT

Resources to translate research towards societal impact.

- OCTRI Awards partners with Business Oregon to offer SBIR/STTR application support to small businesses developing healthcare technologies.
 - 16 Oregon companies
 - \$9.1M SBIR/STTR funding
 - Highest NIH SBIR/STTR funding rate in the US at 22% from 2012-2021

- ORPRN leverages the \$100K invested via CORE to help secure \$8M in annual funding, encompassing 50+ active projects and ~40 Extension for Community Health Outcome programs in Oregon.

- ORPRN and OCTRI received a CARE for Health Award from the NIH Office of the Director due to close integration of our PBRN and CTSA hub. Oregon is collaborating with the PBRN and CTSA in WA state to address health issues in rural communities.
 - 1 of 3 award recipients nationally in 2024
 - \$2.5M NIH funding

SATISFACTION

OCTRI approaches user satisfaction with surveys and targeted follow up interviews. In 2023-24, this led to 1) reorganized support of the REDCap team and 2) improved Informatics project communication plans and intra-OHSU marketing strategies.